

Rowan University

Helipad Detection and Localization From Satellite Imagery: An Enhanced Deep Learning Approach

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**WIRELESS WORLD
RESEARCH FORUM**

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**Federal Aviation
Administration**

OUTLINE

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2. Data Collection Process
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5. Helipad Database Updating Process
6. Q&A

Project Background

Challenges:

- The FAA ADIP 5010 was partially updated;

Objectives:

- Develop a segmentation deep learning approach to detect and segment helipads from satellite imagery.
- Update the FAA ADIP 5010 dataset.

Prior Work

Model: YOLO V3
Precision: 76%

Image.a: Correct detection of helipad from satellite imagery

Image.b: False detection of helipad from satellite imagery

Image.c: False detection of helipad from satellite imagery

Data Collection

	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
	Owner Address	Owner City, State, Zip	Owner Phone	Manager	Manager Address	Manager City, State, Zip	Manager Phone	ARP Latitude	ARP Latitude Sec	ARP Longitude	ARP Longitude Sec
1	51 BRISTOW WAY	TITUSVILLE, FL 32780	321-267-8780	KEVIN DAUGHERTY, AAE	355 GOLDEN KNIGHTS BLVD	TITUSVILLE, FL 32780	321-267-8780	028-30-53.3000N	102653.3000N	080-47-57.2000W	0290877.2000W
2	212-1 CESSNA BLVD	PORT ORANGE, FL 32128	(386) 760-5884	JIM STONE	212-1 CESSNA BLVD	PORT ORANGE, FL 32128	(386) 275-1894	029-04-48.7000N	104688.7027N	081-47-57.2000W	0290877.2000W
3	ST. PETE-CLEAR WATER	CLEARWATER, FL 33762	727-453-7800	THOMAS JEWsbURY	ST PETE-CLEAR WATER	CLEARWATER, FL 33762	727-453-7800	027-54-31.0000N	100471.0810N	081-47-57.2000W	0290877.2000W
4	PO BOX 22287	TAMPA, FL 33622	(813) 870-8776	BRETT W FAY, C.M.	PO BOX 22287	TAMPA, FL 33622	(813) 870-8735	028-00-50.3500N	100850.3540N	081-47-57.2000W	0290877.2000W
5	2300 VIRGINIA AVE	FT PIERCE, FL 34982-5652	772-462-1732	ERIC J. KONUPKA, C.M.	3000 CURTIS KING BOULEVARD	FT PIERCE, FL 34946	772-462-1727	027-29-50.9000N	098998.9080N	081-47-57.2000W	0290877.2000W
6	PO BOX 2286	UMATILLA, FL 32784-2286	352-669-3125	SCOTT BLANKENSHIP	PO BOX 2286	UMATILLA, FL 32784-2286	352-669-3125	028-55-27.1900N	104127.1950N	081-47-57.2000W	0290877.2000W
7	2725 JUDGE FRAN JAMESON	VIERA, FL 32940	(321) 633-2001	STEVE BOROWSKI	1 PILOT'S PLACE	VALKARIA, FL 32950	321-952-4590	027-57-39.1200N	100659.1160N	081-47-57.2000W	0290877.2000W

Fig.1 ADIP

Fig.2 CSV file

Fig.3

Map Size Parameter:

✓ 200 x 200 m

✓ 300 x 300 m

500 x 500 m

Multi Scale Images:

2000 x 2000 px

3000 x 3000 px

Map size=200 x 200 m

4000 x 4000 px

Ultimate Collected Dataset

Dataset : 4596 satellite helipad images.

Map size:

- 200x200 m (50%)
- 300x300 m (50%)

Resolution: {2kx2k , 3kx3k, 4kx4k} px

Dataset diversity:

- Rural and Urban
- Rectangular, Circular and Triangular

Circular Helipad

Rural View

Urban View

Data Augmentation:

We applied only two methods of data augmentation:

- Random horizontal flip.
- Random brightness.

a. Original Image

b. Horizontal Random Flip

c. Random Brightness

Literature Review: Negative Sample Incorporation to Trainset

Incorporating Negative Sample Training for Ship Detection Based on Deep Learning

Laboratory of Digital Earth Science, Institute of Remote Sensing and Digital Earth, Chinese Academy of Sciences

Source : *Sensors* 2021, 19(3), 684;
<https://doi.org/10.3390/s19030684>

A Deep Learning Approach For Airport Runway Detection and Localization From Satellite Imagery

Electrical and Computer Engineering Dept.
Rowan University, NJ, USA

Source : *IEEE*, p 619-623:
[10.1109/ISCC58397.2023.10217868](https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCC58397.2023.10217868)

Negative Sample Collection

Negative Samples incorporated to trainset : 370 helicopter parking spot images.

Sample labeled images

- Polygon coco format was used in labeling since it shows very high precision in labeling task.
- 4928 helipad instances were generated after labeling .

a. Rectangular helipad sample

b. Circular helipad sample

Negative Sample Labeling

Source: *Sensors* **2021**, 19(3), 684; <https://doi.org/10.3390/s19030684>

Training & Test Dataset

Training Set:

- 4774 helipad instances
- 270 parking spot images
- Resolution : {2000, 3000, 4000} px
- Map size: {200 , 300}m

Test Set:

- 154 helipad instances
- 100 parking spot images
- Resolution : {2000, 3000, 4000} px
- Map size: {200 , 300}m

Testset Characteristics

a. Poor condition helipads

b. Under construction helipads

Segmentation Model: Mask R-CNN

- High accuracy and precision
- Flexibility (detection and segmentation)

Mask R-CNN Fine-Tuning

Training Configuration:

- **Backbone** : ResNet-X101, ResNet-50
- **Batch size** = 16
- **Iteration** = 25 000 (42 epochs)
- **Learning rate** = 0.0001
- **Optimizer** = SGD
- **Momentum** = 0.9
- **Weight decay** = 0.00005
- **BATCH_SIZE_PER_IMAGE*** = 512 proposals

(*) Number of Rols per image per batch during training.

Mask R-CNN Performance Comparison

Backbone Architecture	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	mAP %	Test Dataset Size
R-50	0.88	0.91	0.90	89	154
X-101	↑ 0.92	↑ 0.97	↑ 0.94	↑ 92	154

Evaluation Table

$TP = 141$	$FN = 13$
$FP = 18$	$TN = 136$

Confusion Matrix (R-50)

$TP = 149$	$FN = 5$
$FP = 12$	$TN = 142$

Confusion Matrix (X-101)

Visual Results: TP

Visual Results: TP

Image. a

Image. b

Visual results: FP

Results Discussion

Closed helipad not segmented

FAA ADIP 5010 Dataset Updating Process

Helipad

(x, y, w, h) px

bbox coordinates in pixels

Helipad

(xc, yc) px

bbox center coordinates in pixels

Helipad

(Lat, Lon)

bbox center lat and lon coordinates

[Source: coordinate reference system WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator -- Spherical Mercator: Google Maps, OpenStreetMap, ArcGIS, ESRI](#)

The Updated FAA ADIP 5010 Dataset

ARP Latitude DD	ARP Longitude DD			BBox Center	Updated Lat	Updated Lon
47.61777777 77778	-122.200058 333333			(606.49218 75, 518.891845	47.61808481	-122.200342 2
39.35872408 613892	-74.4346368 3368634			(777.02624 51171875, 514.868652	39.35903646	-74.4345902 3
39.35872408 613892	-74.4346368 3368634			(778.79467 7734375, 976.895751	39.35842265	-74.4345871 8
46.98765555 55556	-120.537819 444444			(754.42370 60546875, 734.808105	46.98767574	-120.537810 8
46.42666666 66667	-117.058055 555556			No bbox found!	No helipad here	No helipad here
47.62166666 66667	-122.344722 222222			(776.29089 35546875, 622.103637	47.62183658	-122.344670 21
48.15332777 77778	-122.233919 444444			No bbox found!	No helipad here	No helipad here

Updated FAA database csv file

Helipad Detection Web App Interface

Helipad Detection And Localization

Enter API Key:

Upload CSV file

Drag and drop file here
Limit: 20MB per file • CSV

output.csv 26.1KB

File uploaded successfully!

Run Script

Display Map

Run Script

Display Map

500 km
300 mi

Leaflet | Data by © OpenStreetMap, under ODbL, Google

Helipad Detection Web App Map

Rowan University

Thank You For Your Attention !

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Questions & Answers

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Helipad Centroid Coordinates Conversion

$$\text{latitude} = \text{center}_{\text{lat}} + \frac{Y_{\text{offset}} \times \text{meters per pixel}(\rightarrow_x)}{\text{lat_conversion_factor}}$$

$$\text{longitude} = \text{center}_{\text{lon}} + \frac{X_{\text{offset}} \times \text{meters per pixel}(\rightarrow_y)}{\text{long_conversion_factor} \times \cos(\text{center}_{\text{lat}})}$$

- **center_lat**: Latitude of the center of the image.
- **center_lon**: Longitude of the center of the image.
- **meters_per_pixel**: the conversion factors for meters per pixel in the x or y directions.
- **X_offset**: Offset in pixels in the x-direction from the center of the image.
- **Y_offset**: Offset in pixels in the y-direction from the center of the image.
- **Lat_conversion_factor** = 150543.26
- **Long_conversion_factor** = 149999.05

[Source: WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator -- Spherical Mercator: Google Maps, OpenStreetMap, ArcGIS, ESRI](#)

Data labeling for segmentation

Source: <https://github.com/wkentaro/labelme>

Results Discussion: Parking Spots FP

Parking spot were segmented

Parking spots were not segmented

Model Selection

Resnet Depth	Train Time (s/iter)	Inference Time (s/im)	Train Memory (GB)	Bbox Coco AP	Mask Coco AP
Mask R-50	0.261	0.043	3.4	41.0	37.2
Mask R-101	0.340	0.056	4.6	42.9	38.6
Mask X-101	0.690	0.103	7.2	44.3	39.5

Facebook AI Research Detectron Model Zoo

Source : github.com/facebookresearch/detectron2/blob/main/MODEL_ZOO.md

